

Microcanonical Energy Approach to Generalized Statistical Mechanics

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In previous notes, we considered generalized two body scattering:
 $g(f(e_1))g(f(e_2)) = g(f(e_3))g(f(e_4))$ (a) leading to $\ln(g(f(e_i))) = -(e_i - u)/T$ if one links (a) to conservation of energy during scattering. For $g=1$, one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Here, $f(e_i)$ is the average number of particles with energy e_i . Thus, an averaging has already been done and one needs to know the nature of this average. For example, for $g=f/(1-f)$, the Fermi-Dirac case, it seems the averaging allows for different values of N , the total number of particles, whereas $(e_i - u)/T$ is associated with allowing for different total energies. Thus, the generalized approach of (a) seems to usually be associated with the grand canonical approach in which both total E and N are allowed to vary.

In a previous note (1), we tried to develop a microcanonical approach to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution which replaced $\exp(-e_i/T)$ (which is related to the canonical approach) with another energy function more related to fixed energy. This result, however, only held for e of the same order as E (i.e. small N systems). For $e \ll E$, $\exp(-e/T)$ emerged as a good approximation. In this note, we attempt to apply these same ideas to generalized scattering. Thus, we leave N free, but try to restrict E so this neither really a canonical nor grand canonical approach.

Reaction Balance

One may readily obtain an “average” reaction balance by considering $f(e_i)$, the average number of particles in state e_i . For the MB case, $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$. Taking \ln of both sides and linking to $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, yields $f(e_i)=\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$. For more general cases, one may suggest replacing $f(e_i)$ with $g(f(e_i))$ where $g=1$ for the MB case, $g=f/(1+f)$ for the Bose-Einstein and $g=f/(1-f)$ for the Fermi-Dirac.

It may be useful to link reaction balance to physical scattering in a system. $f(e_i)$ is an average value associated with an average of many energy arrangements treated as one fixed equilibrium state that exists at a point in time, whereas there are many real states each of which exist at an instant in time. Only through averaging may one create a fictitious equilibrium state (at least for smaller numbers of particles). For a large number of particles with small fluctuations, the equilibrium state describes reality closely.

Consider the Fermi-Dirac case and a scattering scenario: $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. Next, focus on the forward reaction which may only occur if e_1 and e_2 have occupations of 1 and e_3 and e_4 of 0. Consider the 16 scenarios related with such a reaction in the form $(e_1, e_2) (e_3, e_4)$:
(1,1), (0,0), (1,0), (0,1) with (1,1), (0,0), (1,0), (0,1). Only for (1,1) with (0,0) will a reaction occur i.e. 1/16 th of the time. If one considers particles to be independent, one may calculate $f(e_i)$ for the 16 cases. One may immediately note that these 16 cases already violate total particle number, for example (1,1,1,1) represents 4 particles while (0,0,0,0) 0. The variable particle number forces a correlation with other energy states, but if one wants all energy states e_i to be

independent, one must allow for variable N (total number of particles). One sees that $f(e_i) = \frac{2}{3}$. Thus: $f(e_1)f(e_2)[1-f(e_3)][1-f(e_4)] = (\frac{2}{3})(\frac{2}{3})(\frac{1}{3})(\frac{1}{3}) = \frac{4}{81}$ which only approximates $1/16$. Thus, reaction balance is at best an approximation.

Out of interest, imagine that given B cases of e_1 and e_2 occupied regardless of the occupation of e_3 and e_4 , only \sqrt{B} lead to reactions (based on some kind of issues with e_1 and e_2 interacting). How may one consider such a case? Perhaps one may construct an ensemble of B systems, each with (1,1) and only allow for a reaction in \sqrt{B} of them. (One may scale B so that one has whole numbers.) By using the equilibrium reaction balance approach, one would use: $\sqrt{f(e_1)f(e_2)} [1-f(e_3)][1-f(e_4)]$.

The idea, however, seems to be that for an equilibrium scenario, one would not only expect $f(e_i)$ values, but average reaction balance equations to hold as well. Otherwise, the average equilibrium $f(e_i)$ fictitious state would favor certain reactions more than others, implying a shift away from equilibrium. For the MB case, it seems that $\langle f(e_i)f(e_j) \rangle = \langle f(e_i) \rangle \langle f(e_j) \rangle$ suggesting particle numbers for each e_i are independent. This is not strictly true for an isolated system it seems, but hopefully is a good approximation.

Total E and N in the Reaction Balance Approach

It seems one must be careful with the reaction balance approach because it uses $f(e_i)$ which is based on independent average values. For example, even in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case: $f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_k)f(e_l)$ may be applied to e_i+e_j which exceeds E total. Thus, MB already seems to be a canonical approach. In general, the reaction approach may violate both total N and total E, thus leading to a grand canonical situation. This seems to be the case if one considers the FD and BE generalized reaction balance cases:

$$\ln\{f/(1-f)\} = -(e_i-u)/T \text{ and } \ln(f/(1+f)) = -(e_i-u)/T \quad ((1))$$

The term $(e_i-u)/T$ arises by linking $g(f(e_1))g(f(e_2)) = g(f(e_3))g(f(e_4))$ with the conservation of energy equation $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. Even though this equation conserves energy in a two body collision, it does not mean energy overall is fixed as it is treating each reaction in the fictitious averaged equilibrium scenario which exists at an instant in time as independent.

One may ask whether one may replace ((1)) with a more microcanonical approach with respect to total energy E. N has already been allowed to vary.

Microcanonical Approach with Respect to E

In a previous note (1), we argued one may develop a somewhat microcanonical approach for the MB distribution. One imagines that E/a is the smallest amount of energy transferable in a reaction (where a is a constant) and that one has V partitions. Then, the number of arrangements is:

$$(E/a+V-1)! / [(E/a)! (V-1)!] \quad ((2))$$

If one removes e/a units of energy, then ((2)), with E/a replaced by $E/a - e/a$, yields the number of remaining arrangements. For e small compared to E (and using Stirling's approximation) one may show that $P(e)$ is proportional to $\exp(-e/T)$ where T is a constant. If it is not small compared with E , $(E - e)^x$ where x is a constant seems to represent $P(e)$.

In this note, we argue such a microcanonical approach for E may be applied to generalized scattering. Thus, for small average N systems, and e small compared with E , one has the usual:

$\ln(g(f(e_i))) = -(e_i - u)/T$, but for large e_i somewhat similar to E (say $E/6$ etc) one would have:

$$g(f(e_i)) = C (E - e_i)^x \quad ((4))$$

At first glance, it seems using a generalized reaction balance $g(f(e_1)) g(f(e_2)) = g(f(e_3)) g(f(e_4))$, taking \ln of both sides and linking with $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ (which does exist) forces the form: $g(f(e_i)) = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$. We argue, however, that a canonical approach is used implicitly for reaction balance, i.e. one may take any $g(f(e_i))$ with another $g(f(e_j))$ and consider a reaction which may never physically occur. For an extreme example using the MB case, consider $f(E) = C \exp(-E/T)$ where E is the total energy of the system. $f(E)$ has a value and may react with $f(e_1)$, according to the average reaction balance approach, but such a scheme assumes one has dropped the restriction of overall total energy E . In the microcanonical energy approach, one considers arrangements of pieces of E/a and allots them to the fictitious entity $g(f(e_i))$ which plays the role of a kind of averaged generalized MB particle in a generalized system. This allows one to arrive at ((4)) which seems to be an average over all N , but not all E for e of the same order as E . For systems with a very large number of N , one would not use ((4)) because a single particle would never really have an energy even close to E total. For example, $e_{ave} = 3/2 RT$ but $E_{total} = 3/2 NRT$. Thus, e may be many times larger than T , but still tiny compared with E total. ((4)) seems to apply to cases where e is of the same order as E total (even $E/10$) for example. Such extreme e values may be associated with evaporation in small N systems with generalized kinematics such as FD or BE or some other scenario.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to "force" ideas of a microcanonical E approach for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case onto generalized reaction balance situations (which apply to fermions, bosons and other cases). The generalized reaction balance has already dropped the restriction on N (the total number of particles, as in the grand canonical case), but by using the microcanonical E approach, we try to place a restriction on the total energy. This seems to have an effect only if e , the energy of a single particle, is of the same order as the total energy in the system. This would only occur, it seems, for statistical systems with few particles (say 100 or fewer) etc. Thus, one seems to have a new approximation scheme which is neither fully canonical nor grand canonical, but only for small N systems. Nevertheless, small systems are considered in the literature and are applied to physical cases.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Microcanonical Derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2020)